

Some Studies on Oscillatory Chemical Reaction of Acetone Dicarboxylic Acid—Cerium—Bromate System

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Aqueous acetone dicarboxylic acid is formed when citric acid is oxidised with Ce^{IV} upto two-electron oxidation stage. This aqueous acetone dicarboxylic acid has been used as an organic substrate in investigating B-Z type oscillatory reaction system along with cerium and bromate in sulphuric acid medium. The effects of varying the concentrations of different components and temperature of the system on time of initiation, time period, life-time and amplitude of oscillations have been studied. The stoichiometry of the reaction is suggested on the basis of experimental results.

THE oscillations in the concentration of some intermediate species during metal ion catalysed oxidation of organic compound having active methylene group by acid bromate is known¹⁻³ as Belousov-Zhabotinskii reaction. Several investigators⁴⁻⁸ have reviewed B-Z reaction to help the current state of our knowledge of chemical oscillators. A generalised mechanism which led to oscillatory behaviour have been given⁹⁻¹⁰ by Field *et al.* However, a close survey of literature could only trace a mere mention^{2,3} being made of capability of acetone dicarboxylic acid in monitoring the oscillations in B-Z reaction; but no systematic study has been reported.

The difficulty in acquiring pure sample of acetone dicarboxylic acid, high cost of imported variety and its easily decomposing nature compelled the author to prepare a fresh sample either in aqueous or crystalline state whenever needed. It was thought of being formed in aqueous state as one of the intermediate oxidation products of citric acid. The present communication gives the justification of holding two-electron oxidation product of citric acid as acetone dicarboxylic acid on one hand whereas on the other, the results of the study of oscillatory characteristics of the system involving this product along with Ce^{III} and bromate is furnished.

Experimental

Confirmation of presence of acetone dicarboxylic acid in aqueous mixture of citric acid and ceric salt:

Citric acid, ceric ammonium nitrate and sulphuric acid were of AnalaR grade. The solutions of 1/180 M citric acid and oxidant 1/10 M Ce^{IV} were prepared in 1.5 M sulphuric acid medium. The redox titration was carried out at 26° by the modified method of Gyani and Prasad¹¹. The

measurements of e.m.f. were taken on a digital potentiometer at different time intervals till the system at each stage showed no fluctuation in its potential.

Study of oscillatory characteristics of acetone dicarboxylic acid in solution A:*

The mixture of 1/180 M citric acid (10 ml) and 1/10 M Ce^{IV} sulphate solutions (1.1 ml) (both prepared in 1.5 M H_2SO_4 medium) and allowed to stand for 2 h is termed solution A* which is known to contain acetone dicarboxylic acid in aqueous state as reported above.

The following stock solutions were prepared. (i) The mixture termed solution A* prepared as given above was found to be equivalent to 0.0056 M acetone dicarboxylic acid along with 0.0056 M Ce^{III} sulphate in 1.5 M sulphuric acid. (ii) The stock solution of oxidiser was prepared also in 1.5 M sulphuric acid using potassium bromate (Baker, A.R.). The above solutions were stored in a thermostat ($\pm 0.05^\circ$). The measurements of e.m.f. of each system was made on a digital potentiometer taking care to avoid chloride ion in the entire setup as it was reported² to inhibit oscillatory phenomenon. An interesting periodic change of colouration was also observed when the indicator Fe^{II} -phenanthroline was included in the reacting system. With the help of graphs of e.m.f. against time, the time of initiation, time period, life-time and amplitude of oscillations were calculated.

For studying the effect of change of concentration of acetone dicarboxylic acid keeping rest of the reactants in same condition, solution A* could be of little use. In this case it was replaced by the solution of freshly prepared¹² crystals of acetone dicarboxylic acid in 1.5 M sulphuric acid with appropriate amount of Ce^{III} sulphate.

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Results and Discussion

Confirmation of the presence of acetone dicarboxylic acid in aqueous mixture of citric acid and ceric salt :

Fig. 1, a graph of e.m.f. vs volume of Ce^{IV} ion, showed a very sharp inflexion on 1.1 ml consumption of oxidant by 10 ml citric acid in a system stored for 2 h after mixing. This amount was

Fig. 1. Plots of potentiometric titration of citric acid at 27° : (a) 0.5, (b) 2, (c) 4, (d) 20 and (e) 24 h.

calculated to be corresponding to the amount of oxidant required to bring about oxidation of citric acid upto two-electron oxidation stage. The result thus suggested the formation of acetone dicarboxylic acid according to the equation (1),

However, it is to be noted here that the reaction is carried upto a first few stages only as the entire interest of the performer was centred around the two-electron oxidation products only. The presence of acetone dicarboxylic acid was then confirmed by some qualitative tests¹²⁻¹⁵ performed in the ethereal extract of a mixture having same constituents in the same proportion but two hundred times stronger than those used in the titration. This led to employ the above mixture in said proportions in most of our studies made.

Study of oscillatory characteristics of acetone dicarboxylic acid in solution A :*

Temperature variation : The effect of change in temperature on oscillatory characteristics is shown in Table 1. In this Table and all the subsequent Tables, the abbreviation Ac(COOH)₃ is used for acetone dicarboxylic acid, *t*_{in} for time of initiation,

t for time period, *t*₁ for life-time and Amp for amplitude of oscillations.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON OSCILLATIONS

[Ac(COOH)₃]=0.0056 M, [Ce^{III}]=0.005 M, [KBrO₃]=0.03 M, H₂SO₄=1.5 M

Sl. no.	Tem. °C	<i>t</i> _{in}		<i>t</i>		<i>t</i> ₁		Amp mV
		min	s	min	s	min	s	
1.	20	4	45	2	50	70	00	90
2.	26	3	25	2	20	58	00	180
3.	33	2	45	1	40	44	15	180

It was observed that the effect of temperature was quite marked. With a slight increase in temperature, the values of *t*_{in}, *t*, and *t*₁ decreased sharply whereas the amplitude increased. This result was supported kinetically also. The rise in temperature and in turn the rise in kinetic energy of the system increased the speeds of component reactions resulting into frequenting the oscillations with life-time cut short.

Concentration of bromate variation :

It may be observed from Table 2 that *t*_{in}, *t* and *t*₁ decrease with the increase in concentration of bromate. The amplitude remained practically constant. The reaction studied has two main parts,

TABLE 2—DEPENDENCE OF OSCILLATIONS ON CONCENTRATION OF BROMATE

[Ac(COOH)₃]=0.0056 M, [Ce^{III}]=0.005 M, [H₂SO₄]=1.5 M, Temp.=26±0.05°

Sl. no.	[KBrO ₃] M	<i>t</i> _{in}		<i>t</i>		<i>t</i> ₁		Amp mV
		min	s	min	s	min	s	
1.	1.5 × 10 ⁻³	4	10	3	50	90	00	175
2.	3.0 × 10 ⁻³	3	25	2	20	53	00	180
3.	6.0 × 10 ⁻³	1	05	1	40	26	00	180

The system exhibits oscillatory phenomenon till the bromate remains in the system to an appreciable extent. High concentration of bromate makes it readily available for repeated production of Ce^{IV} in the system and the latter oxidises the organic substrate fairly rapidly, thereby shortening *t* and *t*₁.

Variation in concentration of acid medium : Sulphuric acid media of different concentrations were made and the stock solutions were prepared in each medium.

The oscillatory characteristics decreased with the increase in concentration of acid (Table 3). The oscillations were detected within a narrow range of acid concentration (0.5–2 M). They were quite sluggish at lower concentrations and are practically undetectable below 0.5 M. The reason may be due

to the fact that both the reactions (2 and 3) are retarded considerably at lower acid strengths. Considering the amplitude, the oscillations were most prominent in 1.5 M acid medium. The medium higher than 2 M is not favourable. This may be attributed to decomposition of acetone dicarboxylic acid at high acidity into products incapable of monitoring oscillations in the conditions employed.

TABLE 3—DEPENDENCE OF OSCILLATORY CHARACTERISTICS ON CONCENTRATION OF ACID MEDIUM

$[\text{Ac}(\text{COOH})_2] = 0.0056 \text{ M}$, $[\text{Ce}^{\text{III}}] = 0.005 \text{ M}$,
 $[\text{KBrO}_3] = 0.03 \text{ M}$, $\text{Temp.} = 26 \pm 0.05^\circ$

Sl. no.	$[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ M	t_{in}		t		t_1		Amp mV
		min	s	min	s	min	s	
1.	2.0	2	00	0	35	30	00	100
2.	1.5	3	25	2	20	53	00	180
3.	0.75	4	50	3	30	58	00	125
4.	0.5	9	20	8	00	70	00	60

Concentration of acetone dicarboxylic acid variation: It was found from Table 4 that there is no significant change in time period of oscillation by varying the concentration of acetone dicarboxylic acid.

TABLE 4—DEPENDENCE OF OSCILLATORY CHARACTERISTICS ON CONCENTRATION OF ACETONE DICARBOXYLIC ACID

$[\text{KBrO}_3] = 0.03 \text{ M}$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 1.5 \text{ M}$, $[\text{Ce}^{\text{III}}] = 0.005 \text{ M}$,
 $\text{Temp} = 26 \pm 0.05^\circ$

Sl. no.	$[\text{Ac}(\text{COOH})_2]$ M	t_{in}		t		t_1		Amp mV
		min	sec	min	sec	min	sec	
1.	0.0031	4	20	1	55	59	00	75
2.	0.0062	3	00	1	10	55	30	150
3.	0.0125	1	15	1	10	18	30	100
4.	0.0166	0	50	1	00	12	00	55

The time of initiation decreased gradually with the increase in $[\text{Ac}(\text{COOH})_2]$. It may be due to the fact that higher concentration of organic substrate could make the repeated conversion of Ce^{IV} to Ce^{III} much easier and thereby faster too.

The system studied closely resembled Belousov's reaction. Field, Koros and Noyes have investigated the oscillations in bromate—cerium—malonic-acid system thoroughly and have elucidated^{8,9,10,17}, the mechanistic details consisting of reaction steps kinetically feasible. As the bromine species and metal ion catalyst are the same in the system studied by us and the results are also in good agreement with them, the similar steps seem to involve here. The interpretation of chemistry could involve three virtually irreversible overall processes,

Formic acid was identified in the end-products of the oscillating system studied by chromatographic technique. Titrating formic acid mercurimetrically¹⁸ it was found that two moles of formic acid formed per mole of acetone dicarboxylic acid consumed. The results of redox titration of acetone dicarboxylic acid revealed that oxidation of $\text{Ac}(\text{COOH})_2$ could proceed upto twelve electron stage only and could not proceed any further even on prolong storage of reaction mixture. Noyes and Jwo¹⁹ had reported that formic acid is inert towards one electron oxidant like Ce^{IV} . The wet analysis of the products of titration at different oxidation stages showed the presence of ketonic and aldehydic intermediates. All these observations helped suggest the stoichiometry of the reaction process (C) to be as

The above two reactions are believed to proceed via several intermediates having ketonic, aldehydic and carboxylic acid groups. The completion of (C) effects the return of control of system to (A) by regenerating bromide ion. This followed by (B) and finally (C) completes the cycle. The cycle is repeated till any of the reactants is depleted. In our study $[\text{KBrO}_3] \gg [\text{Ac}(\text{COOH})_2]$, so it seemed likely that complete consumption of organic substrate brought the oscillatory phenomenon to cease after a while.

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